

Recognition of errors in gaze-based interaction with anomaly detection

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Abstract

Gaze-based interaction provides an intuitive way to control robotic systems, but unintended selections remains a challenge. Conventional approaches mitigate this problem by requiring additional confirmation actions, yet incorrect decisions still occur. In this study, we propose an anomaly detection approach to improve selection accuracy. We conducted a virtual reality experiment with a visual search task and tested different methods to find anomalies in the gaze pattern. These methods are trained with correct selections to learn their features. By exploiting the gaze patterns, the methods effectively discriminate between correct and incorrect selections, since unintended inputs are not well represented in the learned gaze patterns and therefore the features differ from the normal case. The results show that our approach maintains over 90% accuracy for correct selections while successfully identifying over 60% incorrect selections, thereby reducing false activations. To further validate our method, future work should investigate its effectiveness in real-time scenarios.

CCS Concepts

• **Human-centered computing** → **Human computer interaction (HCI)**; *Virtual reality*; • **Computing methodologies** → **Artificial intelligence**.

Keywords

eye tracking, human-computer interaction, autoencoder, deep learning, error detection

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1 Introduction

Gaze-based interaction offers intuitive and hands-free communication with systems [Severitt et al. 2024a; Sidenmark et al. 2021]. This input modality is highly accessible, especially in scenarios where traditional input devices, such as keyboards or joysticks, are impractical or not feasible. The applications where gaze-based interaction can offer support range from assistive technologies for people with disabilities to novel interfaces in augmented or virtual reality.

However, one main challenge in gaze-based interaction is the ‘Midas Touch’ problem [Jacob 1990], where not every gaze conveys an intention. Without additional mechanisms to confirm the user’s choice, the system can struggle to distinguish between an accidental gaze and a deliberate command. A common solution is to use a two-step process: Gaze for selection and another modality, such as head orientation [Sidenmark and Gellersen 2019], nodding [Špakov and Majaranta 2012], or specific eye movements [Esteves et al. 2015] for confirmation. In our previous study [Severitt et al. 2025], we analyzed these confirmation methods and found that while they improve usability, there are still false selections. Therefore, more intelligent processing algorithms for deciphering selections is necessary to improve current approaches.

The consequences of selection errors go beyond mere inconvenience; they disrupt the user experience [Padovani et al. 2019] and can undermine trust in human-robot systems [Flook et al. 2019]. As shown in [Severitt et al. 2024b], selection errors can often be identified by analyzing eye movement patterns shortly after a selection, with increased movement observed in error cases. Building off of this research, our current study investigates whether similar indicators in the eye movements, in a time window shortly before and after the selection, can provide reliable indications of the user’s intention. By incorporating real-time error detection, gaze-based systems can become more robust, reduce the effects of incorrect

selections, and dynamically adapt to user behavior. Moreover, we present a new perspective on error detection, where we frame the error as an anomaly in the gaze behavior, becoming a one class classification approach.

2 Related work

Interaction with assistive robotic systems is trust critical, and user’s perception of error magnitude or occurrences can heavily impact their feelings of security [Kok and Soh 2020; Körber et al. 2018]. Previous studies have shown that summarized eye-tracking statistics can predict both user intention [Bovo et al. 2020; David-John et al. 2021] and error occurrence [Bovo et al. 2020; Bruder et al. 2016; Severitt et al. 2023]. However, these approaches have mainly addressed user error, though system error recognition is equally important for trust maintenance. Naturally, these systems strive for marginal errors, but even one error can place a user in a precarious or unsafe scenario: E.g., accidentally spilling a hot beverage because the robotic arm had a false trajectory. These types of system errors can evoke strong negative user’s perceptions, though can be avoided through realtime gaze features related to the errors. To address this issue, Peacock et al. [2022] has distinguished between input recognition errors and user-initiated actions within as little as 50 to 550 milliseconds after selection using linear regression models. Additionally, human-robot studies have shown that gaze patterns change when system errors occur, such as deviations in focus toward unexpected areas [Aronson and Admoni 2018]. Identifying the most relevant gaze features within these short time frames remains a challenge.

Building on prior research, a Temporal Convolutional Network (TCN) approach has been used to differentiate between user errors, input recognition errors, and intention prediction based on first-order deviations in eye movement data along the x, y, and z axes. This method achieved a performance of up to 68%, significantly surpassing chance-level predictions [Sendhilnathan et al. 2022].

In contrast to the previous literature, we do not classify errors from the temporal gaze patterns, rather we frame errors as a rare occurrence – an *anomaly* in the temporal signal to be detected. We adopted this anomaly detection strategy from time series analysis, where various strategies already exist, as summarized by Schmidl et al. [2022]. Therefore, we detail this approach and evaluated it on our dataset of gaze based target selection in a Virtual Reality (VR) environment.

3 Methods

As our approach of anomaly detection has not been used in the context of user selection intention from temporal gaze signals, we overview four standard machine learning methods as well as an autoencoder architecture. As input, we get timepoints when a selection is detected, we calculate the angle between successive gaze vectors starting 300 ms before the selection and ending 200 ms after. Thus, we have a time series of angles that shows the changes in gaze around the selection. The dataset used for this analysis comes from our previous study [Severitt et al. 2025], and is briefly summarized below. Then, descriptions of the implemented models are provided, and finally, the training and evaluation paradigm are detailed.

3.1 Dataset

The dataset evaluates participants’ performance in a VR based target selection game designed to evaluate different gaze-selection methods. Participants completed timed trials, receiving points for accurate and efficient selections and penalizations for errors. Four selection methods were compared in the study, with customization possible to ensure convenience and ease of use.

Participants. The study included 52 participants (32 men, 18 women, one non-binary person, one person did not wish to provide information) with a minimum age of 18 years and a maximum age of 67 years ($M = 26.63, SD = 9.87$).

VR setup and environment. The environment inside the VR is illustrated in Fig. 1 and further details also about the setup can be found in our previous work [Severitt et al. 2025]. We used the HTC Vive Pro Eye with a built-in Tobii eye tracker with a sampling rate of 120Hz.

Gameplay. For each selection method, ten rounds were played. When a round begins, all robots fly to a new position. When they reach their destination, a blue or green sphere appears on the robots. There is an ‘O’ on all but one of the spheres, the last one has a ‘C’ indicating that it is the correct target. Participants must search for and select this target (illustrated in Fig. 1b and 1c). Once the correct target has been selected, all robots respawn to new positions. For each correct target selected, the reward factors in more points for quicker selection time (maximum 20 points). Incorrect targets selected receive a -21 penalization. Each round times out after 30 seconds, and the participant was able to start and interrupt the round by using the controller.

Study design. For each selection method, the participant begins with a test phase, where they can adjust the method slightly for their personal comfort, e.g., by changing the length of time required to select the target with the gaze. They then performed ten rounds with the preferred settings. The first method was always the gaze dwell method, the order of the other methods was randomized.

Gaze Selection methods. Four different selection methods were compared in the study. The first is the ‘Gaze Dwell’, where the participant only has to look at the target for a certain amount of time to select it. The second was the ‘Gaze and Head’, in which the gaze and head direction must remain on the target for a predefined time. The third method is ‘Nod’ and here a nod was used to confirm the gaze-based selection. The last method called ‘Smooth Pursuit’, since this method was the least popular method and there are only a few misselections [Severitt et al. 2025], it is not part of this work. Since the methods for detecting anomalies are trained separately for each gaze-selection method, for readability of the results, we refer to these as the three separate conditions for the anomaly detection methods.

3.2 Data preprocessing

A total of 520 rounds for each of the three evaluated selection conditions are used for evaluation of our anomaly detection methods. To prepare the data, we first search for both correct and incorrect selections. Then, we take all local combined gaze vectors, which are calculated from the local gaze vector of the left and right eye, from

the case of the one-class SVM, the algorithm is adapted for unsupervised anomaly detection by treating the dataset as a single class (normal data) and learning a decision boundary around it. Instead of distinguishing between multiple classes, the one-class SVM finds a hypersphere or hyperplane that includes most of the normal data while maximizing the margin. Any new data points that fall outside this boundary are considered anomalies. The algorithm relies on kernel functions (e.g. radial basis function) to model complex data distributions, but its performance is very sensitive to the choice of hyperparameters and may require extensive tuning for different data sets. We have used the 'scale' option for gamma, as kernel the 'rbf' and for nu 0.1.

Train and evaluation. We used 70% of the participants as training data, considering only correct selections during training, as this is the standard for these methods. To determine the optimal hyperparameters, we performed a 5-fold cross-validation, split by participant, on the training set and selected the hyperparameters that yielded the highest macro accuracy. Using these chosen hyperparameters, we then trained the final model on the entire training dataset and evaluated its performance on the test dataset of the unseen 30% of participants. A list of all tested hyperparameters can be found in the supplementary materials.

3.3.2 Deep learning-based method: Temporal Convolutional Network Autoencoder (TCNAE). An autoencoder is a type of neural network designed to learn efficient, compressed representations of data by training it to reconstruct its input. It consists of two main parts: An encoder, which compresses the input into a smaller, latent representation, and a decoder, which reconstructs the original input from that representation (see supplementary Fig. 1). By minimizing the difference between the input and the reconstructed output, the autoencoder learns meaningful patterns or features in the data, often used for dimensionality reduction, noise removal, or as a pre-training step for other models.

Architecture. Since we are working with time series data, we used a TCN [Bai et al. 2018] with two layers with output channels 4 and 8 and a kernel size of 3. The dilation of the first layer is 1 and that of the second layer is 2. Each layer is followed by batch normalization layer and a Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation function. The output is then flattened and transferred to the latent feature space of dimension 10 using a fully connected layer. The decoder is the inverse version of the encoder. It starts with a fully connected layer, which transfers the latent representation back to the dimension of the flattened output of the TCN from the encoder. This is followed by a TCN also with two convolutional layers with output channels 4 and 1 which is the dimension of the input. The input channels are 8 and 4. The kernel size is again 3 and the dilations are 1 and 2. Similar to the encoder, the convolutional layers are followed by a batch normalization layer and a ReLU activation function.

Train and evaluation. Similar to the machine learning methods, we split the data set into two subsets: 70% of the participants were used for training and 30% for testing. To determine the optimal hyperparameters for each condition, A 5-fold cross-validation, split by participant, was performed with the training participants. The selected hyperparameters were then evaluated on the test participants

to ensure their effectiveness on completely unseen data. The hyperparameters that achieved the highest mean macro accuracy across all conditions were selected. A list of all tested hyperparameters can be found in the supplementary materials. For model training, the network was trained for 400 epochs with a batch size of 4000. The Mean Squared Error (MSE) was used as the loss function, with a learning rate of 10^{-3} and the Adam optimizer. To set a threshold for detecting incorrect selections, we calculated the MSE values from the training set after training and set the threshold to the 95th percentile. Since only correct selections of the training participants were used during training, the network learns to reconstruct them correctly. During testing, incorrect selections – which the network never encountered during training – lead to a higher reconstruction error, measured as the MSE between input and output.

3.4 Evaluation metrics

To evaluate the performance of the anomaly detection methods, we used four different metrics. Participants can either make a correct or an incorrect selection, with a correct selection being when the correct target is chosen. Based on this, we report the accuracy for each class separately. The class accuracy for correct selections measures how well the method identifies correct selections, while the class accuracy for incorrect choices evaluates the method's ability to recognize incorrect selections.

In addition to these class accuracies, we report the macro-accuracy, which is the average of the two class accuracies, treating them equally regardless of class size. We also report the micro-accuracy, which represents the overall accuracy, considering the proportion of correctly classified instances across all samples. This combination of metrics ensures a balanced evaluation, as both class-specific and overall performance are taken into account.

In addition to evaluating the classification performance, we also assessed the computational efficiency of the individual methods. Since the system is intended for real-time applications, minimal latency is preferred. We measured the prediction time for each method and get the time taken to predict correct or incorrect based on the input. We report the mean time required for a single prediction.

4 Results

We start the results with an overview of the performance of all methods and how the different gaze-selection conditions affect model performance. Then we take a closer look at the best performing model on individual participant performance.

4.1 Summary of all methods

Table 1 presents a comparative analysis of different anomaly detection methods based on their mean prediction time, accuracy for correct and incorrect selections, as well as micro and macro accuracy across all conditions ('Gaze', 'Head and Gaze', 'Nod'). Each method was independently trained for every condition. Among the machine learning-based methods, the One-Class SVM achieved the highest macro accuracy (0.884), demonstrating balanced performance in both correct and incorrect selections. It also recorded the highest incorrect selection accuracy (0.931), indicating good performance in identifying incorrect selections. Additionally, the One-Class SVM

Table 1: Performance comparison of different methods for anomaly detection on the test dataset. The table shows the mean prediction time (in milliseconds) and the mean classification metrics, including correct and incorrect selection accuracy, micro and macro accuracy over all conditions ('Gaze', 'Head and Gaze', 'Nod'). Each method was separately trained for every condition. The best values for each column are highlighted in bold.

Method	Prediction time (ms)	Correct accuracy	Incorrect Accuracy	Micro	Macro
Elliptic Envelope	0.116	0.842	0.914	0.843	0.878
Isolation Forest	18.284	0.846	0.897	0.847	0.872
LOF	31.260	0.864	0.897	0.865	0.881
One-Class SVM	0.080	0.837	0.931	0.838	0.884
TCNAE	0.457	0.897	0.828	0.896	0.861

had the shortest prediction time (0.080 ms), making it the most computationally efficient method. The deep learning-based TCNAE model achieved the highest correct selection accuracy (0.897) and micro accuracy (0.896), indicating good performance in recognizing correct selections. However, its incorrect selection accuracy (0.828) was lower than that of the top-performing machine learning methods. The TCNAE model's prediction time (0.457 ms) was also slightly higher compared to faster machine learning methods, such as the One-Class SVM. While the LOF method showed a balanced performance with a macro accuracy of 0.881, it had a relatively long prediction time (31.260 ms), making it less usable for real-time applications. The Elliptic Envelope, although not leading in accuracy, remained one of the more computationally efficient methods with a prediction time of 0.116 ms. Overall, the results suggest a trade-off between accuracy and computational efficiency. The TCNAE model excels in detecting correct selections, while machine learning models, particularly the One-Class SVM, offer a more balanced performance with minimal computational cost.

We provide a more detailed performance breakdown of the TCNAE model, as it achieved the highest overall accuracy (micro-accuracy: 0.896). In a real-world application, a high overall accuracy is crucial to ensure reliable decision-making. While the conventional methods performed well in certain metrics, the TCNAE showed the best performance in correct selections choices, making it a strong candidate for practical use. It also shows acceptable prediction time (0.457 ms). Despite the slightly lower accuracy on incorrect selections, the ability to generalize to correct selections suggests that it is well suited for practical use.

4.2 Leave one participant out cross validation

Figure 2 shows the results of the leave-one-participant-out analysis, which shows the accuracy of the TCNAE model for the three conditions (gaze, head and gaze, and nod) for correct and incorrect selections. The model achieves consistently high accuracy for correct selections under all conditions. However, the accuracy for incorrect selections is lower compared to the performance of the correct selections, indicating that anomaly detection remains a difficult task. Since the anomaly detection methods were developed specifically to deal with unbalanced data, the slightly lower accuracy for incorrect selections indicates that these anomalies have a different gaze pattern. However, except for the Nod condition, the accuracy for incorrect selections is above 0.70, suggesting the model is still able to detect many of these unique gaze patterns that are different from those of the correct selections. For correct selections,

Figure 2: Results of the leave-one-participant-out analyzes for the TCNAE model. It shows the average accuracy for all runs for the different conditions ('Gaze' (G), 'Head and Gaze' (HaG), 'Nod' (N)) and classes (Correct and Incorrect selections and Macro and Micro).

the results show generally high accuracy, with all conditions over 0.90.

When we look at the performance of the model for each participant (Fig. 2 in the supplementary material), we see an overall high accuracy for correct selections. However, the nod condition shows a bit more variable performance, with some participants achieving near perfect accuracy and others performing less consistently. However, as incorrect selections were relatively rare, accuracy should be interpreted with caution as a single misclassification can have a large impact on the results. Overall, macro accuracy is generally between 70% and 80%, with the model correctly identifying correct selections over 90% of the time for most participants. Thus, in a typical interaction with an assistive system where errors are infrequent, this level of accuracy would be acceptable, as the model reliably identifies correct selections in the vast majority of cases.

5 Discussion

In this paper, we show that standard anomaly detection methods and a more elaborate autoencoder are viable approaches to tackling error detection when an incorrect target is selected in VR gaze-based interaction paradigms. All models achieve high accuracy for both correct selections, with the TCN-based autoencoder showing the highest micro accuracy. Given this achievement and its ability to predict in under one millisecond, we feel this model would be the most suitable for a system running in realtime.

It is notable that the methods we choose are trained on instances where correct user behavior and system response happen. Thus, an error can be easily characterized as having features that do not align with correct instances. This approach is favorable for unbalanced

datasets or realistic scenarios where error occurrence is minimal. Taken in the context of the Midas Touch problem, we provide a more adaptive way to determine an unintentional command. Though, we currently evaluate in a VR visual search game environment, these methods can be easily trained on data in more diverse contexts of accessibility support systems, such as selecting an object for interaction [Narkar et al. 2024].

While these findings are promising, further validation is needed in a real-time experiment. User behavior may adapt when interacting with a system, potentially influencing the interplay of gaze input and system interpretation. Prior research has shown that users adjust their gaze behavior (e.g., secondary saccades) when interacting with systems [Heins and Lappe 2024], which could impact performance over time. Future work should explore this adaptation effect and assess how well the approach generalizes in dynamic, real-time environments. Furthermore, the potential to combine all anomaly detection methods to achieve better results should also be considered. For instance, Zhang et al. [2022] used a reinforcement learning approach to optimize a model selection strategy. If a system has multiple anomaly detection models, an algorithm could select the best one at a given moment.

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